

Start height and vertical loop with an example

Harald Schröder

2015

Which height h does the body achieve with initial velocity v_0 on the loop with radius R ?

We'll treat the frictionless case. In the frictionless case, the bodies slide. This applies to the ball as well.

In chapter 1 at Schröder [1], the loop velocity is:

$$v_{min} = \sqrt{gR \cos \gamma}$$

g is the earth's acceleration.

γ = loop angle $\gamma \in [0^\circ, 180^\circ]$

Energy conservation law: $0 \leq \gamma \leq 90^\circ$

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot mv_{min}^2 + mgR = \frac{1}{2} \cdot mv_0^2 + mgh$$

solved for v_{min} :

$$v_{min}^2 = v_0^2 + 2g \cdot (h - R) \quad (1)$$

the loop formula before:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_{min}^2}{gR} \quad (2)$$

Distinction of cases:

$$\text{first case} \quad v_0^2 + 2g \cdot (h - R) < 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \gamma > 90^\circ$$

$$\text{second case} \quad v_0^2 + 2g \cdot (h - R) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \gamma = 90^\circ$$

$$\text{third case (loop case)} \quad v_0^2 + 2g \cdot (h - R) > 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad 0^\circ \leq \gamma < 90^\circ$$

To the first case: $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 180^\circ$

Energy conservation law:

$$\frac{mv_0^2}{2} + mgh = mgR \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) \quad (3)$$

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{\frac{mv_0^2}{2} + mgh}{mgR} - 1$$

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_0^2}{2gR} + \frac{h}{R} - 1$$

equation (3) transformed:

$$v_0^2 = \frac{mgR \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) - mgh}{\frac{m}{2}} = 2gR \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) - 2gh \quad (4)$$

equation (4) solved for h :

$$h = \frac{2gR \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) - v_0^2}{2g} = R \cdot (1 + \cos \gamma) - \frac{v_0^2}{2g}$$

To the second case: $\gamma = 90^\circ$

$$v_0^2 = 2g \cdot (R - h) \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \frac{v_0^2}{2g} = R - h$$

$$h = R - \frac{v_0^2}{2g}$$

To the third case (loop case): $0^\circ \leq \gamma < 90^\circ$

This case is more complex. It is not enough to insert v_{min} in formula (2). The ball loses kinetic energy. We insert with formula (1) in equation (2):

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_{min}^2 - 2gR \cdot \cos \gamma}{gR}$$

We obtain:

$$3gR \cdot \cos \gamma = v_{min}^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad \cos \gamma = \frac{v_{min}^2}{3gR}$$

with equation (1):

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_0^2 + 2g \cdot (h - R)}{3gR} \leq 1 \quad (5)$$

At a value greater than or equal to 1 the highest point of the loop is reached.

Solvings of (5):

$$v_0^2 = 3gR \cdot \cos \gamma - 2g \cdot (h - R)$$

$$h = \frac{3gR \cdot \cos \gamma - v_0^2}{2g} + R$$

We introduce the radius r of the small ball. If we take the barycenter of the small ball into consideration, then we must insert $R - r$ instead of R in the equations. We assume that the small ball has a (local) constant density.

Exercise:

A ball is started from a height $h = 0.8\text{m}$ with a initial velocity $v_0 = 0.3 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$. The ball rolls on a loop with the radius $R = 0.75\text{m}$. What height angle γ does the ball achieve?

Solution of the exercise:

The start height is $h = 0.8\text{m}$, the initial velocity is $v_0 = 0.3 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}$ and as a loop radius we have $R = 0.75\text{m}$. ($g = 9.81 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2}$)

We must check, if the ball comes to the upper loop half. If this is not true, we have case 1 or case 2. Perhaps there is a solution in the lower loop half (case 1).

We need the formula:

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_0^2}{2gR} + \frac{h}{R} - 1$$

We obtain $\gamma = 85.8^\circ$. But in case 1 it must be $90^\circ \leq \gamma \leq 180^\circ$. We have a false solution. Case 1 is not true.

Now we examine, if $\gamma = 90^\circ$. This is case 2. Then it must be:

$$v_0^2 = 2g \cdot (R - h)$$

The calculation leads to $v_0^2 = 0.09 \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}^2}$ and $2g \cdot (R - h) = -0.981 \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{s}^2}$. Case 2 is not true.

Now we turn to the third case (loop case). We use the following formula (5):

$$\cos \gamma = \frac{v_0^2 + 2g \cdot (h - R)}{3gR}$$

We get $\gamma = 87.2^\circ$. It must be γ from interval $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]$. With that we have the right solution in loop case.

References

- [1] Harald Schröder "The loop" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2002